

FIVE YEAR PLANS AND DAIRY DEVELOPMENT: A REVIEW

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INTRODUCTION:

Milk has long been recognized as the most complete single food available in nature for maintenance of health and proportion of growth of the mammals. It is not exactly known as to when the man began to utilize milk of animals. But it is an agreed fact that the Aryans were the first to domesticate cattle and use their milk as a food, this was as back as 1500 to 2500 B.C. Aryans practice of domestication was being followed by Hindus all over India.

The first official move for organized dairying in the country took place around 1989 by setting up the Military dairy farm at Allhabad and creamery at Anand (Gujarat) for army units and their hospitals for sending bulk butter for troops to Iraq. Apart from the military farms before, 1947 there were 60 private dairy farms, with North Indian Breeds viz. The shiwal, Sindhi and The Tharparkar.

Thus dairy industry in India has developed rapidly during the last few decades, both in terms of total milk production and livestock improvement population. In 1981, India ranked the first amongst the Asian producing countries and now it ranks the first in the world.

On the eve of the First Five-Year Plan, the Aarey Milk Colony was completed and the largest milk processing and bottling plant in the country (25,000 litres per day) went into operation and a few co-operatives in the milk belt of Gujarat, Punjab and Uttar Pradesh were doing well. But systematic development of cattle and dairy industry started only after the launching of the country's five-year plans.

Table 2.11 gives the breakup of planned expenditure during the five-year plans on dairying and animal husbandry.

First Five-Year Plan (1951-1956) :

The first plan was devoted towards (1) controlled breeding, (2) disease control, (3) development of Goshala and (4) Key village schemes. The plan included 27 schemes in different states for dairying and milk supply at an estimated cost of

Rs.78.1 million which was 11.22 per cent of the total plan outlay. Therefore, the target was not achieved and the schemes did not make an anticipated headway.

AAREY Milk Colony, Bombay:

This unique project was established in 1952 by the erstwhile Government of Bombay for several basic reasons. First, to remove the 15000 commercial buffaloes kept in congested stables inside the city. Secondly, quality control could be enforced adequately, if all the milk fist came to the central dairy plant instead of being supplied to the consumers and thirdly, by controlling the price of milk, fourthly to look after the dry cattle and calves in a better manner. And finally, scientific methods in feeding, breeding and management could be applied as well as facilities for training and research could be developed.

Table No. 2.11 Expenditure on Animal Husbandry and Dairying Under Five-Year Plans(Rs. In Millions)

Sr. No.	Expenditure head	I Five year plan	II Five year plan	III annual plan	Three annual plans	IV five year plan	V five year plan	Two annual plan	VI five year plan	VII Five year plan
		1951-56	1956-61	1961-66	1966-69	1969-74	1974-78	1978-80	1980-85	1985-90
1.	Total plan outlay	1960	4600	8573	6626	15778.9	39303.4	N.A.*	97500	322366
2.	Amt. spent on animal husbandry	141.9	385.0	547.0	413.3	940.6	3095.6	N.A.	3896.4	11585.5
3.	Amt. spent on dairying	78.1 (3.98)	190.0 (4.13)	360.5 (4.20)	261.4 (3.94)	1389.7 (8.80)	1279.8 (3.25)	N.A.	4623.0 (4.74)	7117.9 (2.33)
4.	Total (2 + 3) per cent to total plan outlay	220.00 (11.22)	575.0 (12.5)	907.5 (10.58)	674.7 (10.18)	2330.3 (14.76)	4375.4 (11.13)	2669.9 (N.A.)	8519.4 (8.73)	19102.4 (5.92)

Note: *1) Break down not available, 2) Figures in parentheses denote total plan outlay.

Source: Annual Report 1984-85 and Planning Commission Documents on Five Year Plans, Ministry of Agriculture and Co-operative Government of India.

With these objectives in force, some 3200 acres of land comprising the village of Aarey was acquired about 30 Km. North of the center of the city. In the beginning, the milk colony reached 1,20,000 liters of milk per day giving average of 7 liter per buffalo. But the position after 1963 was not satisfactory as the milk yield dropped to a bare 10,000 liters per day, as many licensees left the colony with their animals.

Second Five-Year Plan (1956-1961):

Dairy development on an organized basis began to take shape during this plan period. The expenditure during this plan amounted to Rs. 190.00 million. A number of states created separate dairy development departments to give exclusive attention on the development of dairying. The programme envisaged establishment of 66 fluid milk handling plants and 6 milk product factories. In addition to the existing one at Bangalore, two additional Regional Dairy Research Stations were established at Bombay and Calcutta. It was during this plan that the gift of rail and road milk tankers from Newzealand were received by Bombay Milk Scheme for transportation of milk between Anand and Bombay.

Third Five-Year Plan (1961-1966):

During this plan an allotment of Rs.360.5 million was made. The setting up of 55 fluid milk projects for cities having a population of 1,00,000 each, eight rural creameries, six milk product factories, two cheese factories and four cattle feed factories were set up. At Anand a modern feed mill was set up, with a gift from the United Kingdom. The NDDB was set up in September 1965 with headquarters at Anand. Also ICDP was also introduced in new areas. The dairy development policy in this plan was outlined. The supply and collection of milk was undertaken by a network of producers' co-operatives in the villages. The processing and distribution of milk and milk products was also organised on co-operative line."

Three Annual Plans (1966-1969):

During this plan period the attention was given to the completion of the projects in hand and an expenditure of Rs.261.04 million was incurred.

Fourth Five-Year Plan (1969-1974):

In this plan the attention was given to use the improved dairy technology, management practices and bringing in more plants in the cooperative sector. The total expenditure of Rs. 1389.7 million was made, which was 14.76 per cent of the total expenditure, which was also the highest in all plans so far made. It was during this plan that the Operation Flood Programme was launched, with the help of aid from the World Food Programme.

Fifth Five-Year Plan (1974 - 1978) :

In this plan the animal husbandry and dairy development programmes were developed with a view to give the subsidiary occupation to small and marginal farmers and agricultural labourers. The growth rate of 5 per cent was considered for the milk production with total amount of Rs.4375.4 million on animal husbandry and dairying.

Annual Plans (1978-1980):

The total amount of expenditure on animal husbandry and dairying was Rs.2669.9 million.

Sixth Five-Year Plan (1980-1985):

In this plan more number of development blocks were brought under programmes like DPAP and IRDP. The cross breeding programme of cows in all the milkshed areas under OF were brought in practice. During this plan the second phase of programme was implemented. The stress was also laid on organization of Anand Pattern of Milk Co-operatives in the 'OF' areas. The total amount of; expenditure in this plan was made of Rs.8519.4 millions.

Seventh Five-Year Plan (1985 - 1990) :

In this plan the total outlay was of Rs. 19,102.4 million and the total milk production reached upto 52 million tonnes. The expected rate of growth of milk was

6.5 per cent and the per capita consumption of milk which was 149 grams. The main stress was given on raising milk production, feed and fodder.

If one observes the expenditure on Animal Husbandry and Dairying during the last six plans, it is found that this significant agricultural group on which more than 70 per cent of the population depends has had only 11.3 per cent of the total plan expenditure. Dairying has never been treated as a priority industry and it is doubtful if in the overall planning even livestock will ever receive priority. The attention paid to dairying can be judged from the fact that amount spent on it during the six five-year plans which works out only 4.0 per cent of the total expenditure. Further, the expenditure on dairying has been mostly spent on providing infrastructural facilities such as collection, transport, processing and distribution facilities and very little on production of more milk. Therefore, in future plans, the greater attention should be paid to animal husbandry and dairying.

In earlier times, milk was mostly handled by individual farmers who were oppressed by middlemen. Milch cattle were kept in unhygienic surroundings, milching was unscientific and milk handling was unclean. Dairymen received lower price and they could not sell it in distant places. In this situation, the co-operative organization alone has come forward to safeguard the interest of producers and consumers.

Dairy Development in the Ninth and Tenth Plan :

By the end of the Eighth five-year plan the milk production in India had increased upto 70 million tonnes and in the Ninth five-year plan it had reached upto 84 million tonnes. The per capita availability of milk increased from 112 grams, to 226 grams, per day in 2001-02. However, it is still below the world average of 285 gm. An investment in the dairy sector during the Ninth plan decreased as compared to the eighth plan. Out of 168 milk unions, 58 milk unions (34.5 percent) were running in loss as on March, 2000. Still the policy of the Government during the Tenth plan in dairy sector is to give preference to the establishment of milk processing plant in the co-operative sector. Restrictions on establishing new milk processing plants under Milk and Milk Products Order (MMPO) has now been removed.

During the Tenth plan the target for milk production is set out at 108.4 metric tonnes with annual increase of 6 percent. The allocation for dairying and fishery is Rs. 2,500 crore. The viable and sustainable livestock will be promoted by the Government. The technology support to enhance the productivity will be given and the per unit cost will be lowered down.

Dairy needs to adopt new technology as well as to undertake sanitary

measures. During the tenth plan training of artificial insemination will be

given to the lower level dairy personnel. It is supposed that women will play

an important role in the dairy development and women extension workers will

be involved for the first time in dairy sector. The conservation of native

livestock will be the aim of dairy, enhancement of feed, fodder and

improvement of common property resources will be taken care of. Fodder

development programmes in watershed development areas will also be

undertaken. To maintain the quality and safety of milk products the legislation

will be passed. This legislation will take care of standards corresponding to

Codex Standards. The National Animal Health and Information System will be

established, with the help of Research Institutions, Government Departments,

Panchayati Raj Institutions, Urban Local Bodies, Private Industries, Co-

operatives and NGOs. This will work as National Data Base. The major thrust

will be on genetic up gradation of indigenous cattle and buffaloes.

REFERENCES:

1. Kharody, D.N. (1974): Dairying in India, Asia Publishing House, New Delhi (p. 5-62).
2. Baviskar, B.S. and Attewood D.W. (1984): Rural Co-operatives in India, Sage Publications, New Delhi, p. 80-87.
3. Pawar, S.N. and Koli, P.A. Salunkhe S.A. (2003): UGC Sponsored Major Research Project, p. 15-87.

